

After the Nation-State Project Syndicate

*By Antara Haldar**

CAMBRIDGE – Imagine being regularly beset by viruses for which there are no vaccines. Such is life under the current structures of global governance and international law. Our problems are international, but our solutions are national. Our world is interconnected, but our institutions are siloed or toothless. Under these circumstances, crises are inevitable, chronic, and potentially irresolvable.

Hence, on February 24, 2022, the Russian army invaded Ukraine, violating the supposed sanctity of borders and inaugurating a new era of conflict unlike anything seen since the Cold War, or perhaps even World War II. In or around December 2019, a novel coronavirus surfaced in the Chinese city of Wuhan; rather than notifying the world, Chinese authorities initially hid the outbreak, precipitating a pandemic that ground the global economy to a halt. On September 15, 2008, the collapse of a financial services firm, Lehman Brothers, exposed a systemic risk that no global-governance body had considered, triggering a global cascade of dominos that would take years to clean up. The list could go on.

Social scientists describe these situations as “collective action problems”: everyone has a long-term interest in cooperating but a short-term incentive to act selfishly. Such problems must be addressed with institutions and organizing systems that change individuals’ incentives. Solutions range from privatization (“pay per use” arrangements) to the Leviathan (a strong state that can enforce norms through law) to the emergence of a shared morality.

In thinking about “contagious” global problems, we will need to rethink our notion of the collective. We continue to operate as a collective of nation-states, even though greenhouse-gas emissions, pathogens, nuclear proliferation, and data do not respect territorial sovereignty.

Legal theory might be able to help. Following philosopher H. L. A. Hart, we can think of any legal system [as a union](#) between “primary rules” (rules) and “secondary rules” (“rules about rules”). The importance of primary rules should be obvious. Any group of individuals needs at least some basic rules to survive, which is why pretty much every society has had diktats against murder.

As the solicitor and folklorist E. Sidney Hartland [wrote](#) in 1924, rules restricting individual behavior constitute primitive law, or “customs that governed societies in a lower culture, the customs that governed savage people. The validity of these customs was dependent on their acceptance and recognition, as there were no written laws.”

When we made the transition from pre-legal “primitive” past to “modern” present, a critical mass of us effectively opted in to a meta-rule that allowed behavior to be changed by fiat in the service of the common good. We agreed to confer rule-making power on the sovereign, which could take the form of a person, like an emperor, or an abstraction, like a parliament. A century after Hartland was writing, we owe many of our biggest collective action problems to the fact that our international legal system is still largely “primitive.” To use his antiquated terminology, we as a global community are in a position reminiscent of “savages.”

Fortunately, the origin story of national legal systems may show how we can establish a genuinely effective system of international law. The best way to proceed is through the realm of social cognition, updating how we think of ourselves and our place in a broader community. Just as we once moved from disparate, homogeneous tribes to somewhat arbitrarily designated nation-states, we now must amalgamate our national identities into a morally coherent global polity. That may sound like a big change; but it is a much smaller leap than the one we made when we enshrined the notion of “country” into law and our collective consciousness.

As the political scientist Benedict Anderson famously [put it](#), nations are “imagined communities.” Far from being an organic or natural configuration imbued with inalienable integrity, a nation consists of a *narrative* comprising everything from a selective iconography to constitutions and maps. It is these components that lead the individual psyche to meld into the collective identity that in turn sustains the idea of the nation.

But this process need not culminate in what we call the nation-state. [Research](#) by sociologist Saskia Sassen finds that residents of “global cities” have much more in common with each other than they do with the rest of their compatriots. The collective identities that we assert are based less on empirical facts (like shared history or language) than on social construction. A country like Cameroon, for instance, is an [amalgam](#) of 250 distinct indigenous populations and 200 languages. Moreover, we have already witnessed the evolution of an effective transnational [legal system](#) in the European Union.

Channeling the mood of the Leave camp in the 2016 Brexit referendum, British Prime Minister Theresa May [told](#) that year’s Conservative Party Conference that, “If you believe you are a citizen of the world, you are a citizen of nowhere.” But to embrace nativism is to deny the reality of the world we live in.

“Citizen of the world” is not some new, elitist construct. The concept dates to the fourth century BC, when Greek Cynics and Stoics described themselves as “citizens of the cosmos” (hence the term cosmopolitan). It is thus fitting that one of the leading current attempts to create a cohesive international polity emanates from Greece, in the form of [Yanis Varoufakis’s Progressive International](#).

Moreover, it is simply intuitive that our obligations to others transcend ties of kinship or national citizenship. As the philosopher Kwame Antony Appiah [puts it](#), “boundaries of the nation are morally irrelevant – accidents of history have no rightful claim on our conscience.” Since our most pressing problems can *only* be solved on a planetary scale, what we need is a moral revolution to underwrite a new federalist international institutional structure.

The foundations of our current, broken global governance system were laid during the dark days of the two world wars. The dangers we now face should spur us to reimagine the locus of our communities and create a new alignment of individual and collective interests. An early example can be seen in broad public support for the 2015 Paris climate agreement. To achieve our climate goals, and to solve our other collective action problems, we will need to tell a different story about who we are and where our sovereign is.

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